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Executive Summary

This **Whitebook** was prepared as part of the **COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inter- and intra-regional ecosystems for knowledge production (COOPERATE)** project. It aims to summarise the key outcomes of the project and to develop policy recommendations for the future of ERA Hubs and the way they could contribute to reinforce the ERA.

The COOPERATE project has been funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme with the objective to develop and pilot the European Research Area (ERA) Hub concept, hence implementing the first steps of the ERA Policy Action 15 “Building up research and innovation ecosystems to improve excellence and competitiveness”¹. The aim of the COOPERATE project is to create a methodology to strengthen university-led regional R&I ecosystems across Europe. It **supports the creation and development of ERA Hubs** and aims to **set the basis for the creation of a pan-European network of ERA Hubs**. For this, the COOPERATE project applies **an approach relying on co-creation arenas** in which a broader community of quadruple helix actors (from various ecosystems, types of organisations and levels of governments) interact.

Concept of ERA Hubs in the COOPERATE project

The COOPERATE project defines the ERA Hubs concept as **an ecosystem of quadruple helix actors, led by universities, aiming at improving knowledge valorisation within their region**. The ERA Hubs operate within their broader regional Research & Innovation (R&I) ecosystems, which constitute the background conditions for knowledge valorisation.

The ERA Hub ecosystem of actors would come together through a **structured collaboration mechanism**, whereby a group of individuals representing quadruple (or at least triple) helix actors have regular meetings centred on knowledge valorisation. The objective of these meetings would be to discuss, align and decide on the ecosystem’s needs and priorities, activities and action plans, inter-hub exchanges and fostering cocreation on knowledge valorisation² topics. Such a **flexible and light collaboration mechanism** would be adaptable to diverse types of ecosystems while avoiding the creation of new entities or organisations.

The action would be **led by universities (or university-related entities)**, as these organisations are well-rooted in their regions and are key actors in the creation of knowledge and talent. The university’s role within the ERA Hubs is to lead the organisation of these meetings, but participants from the **quadruple helix would take the leadership** on areas that are closer to their core activities.

¹ <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/policy-agenda-2022-2024/amplifying-access-research-and-innovation-excellence-across-union>

² By taking a regional ecosystem lens, this approach to ERA Hubs would complement the recent actions developed at EU level in the field of knowledge valorisation (e.g. ERA Action 7, the EC Knowledge Valorisation Platform, the Guiding Principles, the Codes of Practice, the Mutual Learning Exercise, etc.).

ERA Hubs can address the need to connect excellent research with users and societal needs

- **Connecting with all relevant stakeholders and involving the whole R&I ecosystem is a key prerequisite for a flourishing knowledge valorisation process**, together with the promotion of an open entrepreneurial culture, better circulation and co-creation of knowledge, mobility of skilled people, and breaking functional and physical silos. The latest version of the Proposal for a Council Recommendation on the European Research Area Policy Agenda 2025-2027 highlights the need to improve “*the articulation between R&I and higher education within the ERA and unleashing the full potential of European R&I ecosystems*”. This point is underlined as a structural policy for the upcoming ERA Policy Agenda.
- **There is a gap in policy attention and action towards fostering knowledge valorisation at the regional level**, even though this is the level where connections and trust are easier to develop, where value and knowledge are created, and where individuals are trained and employed.
- **Universities, as creators of knowledge and talent are in an excellent position to fulfil the role of orchestrators of their regional R&I ecosystems**. Universities are well-rooted in the territory, perceived as neutral actors and have the key to unlock a more fluid and effective communication between knowledge producers (researchers) and knowledge users (business, public sector and civil society). Universities can thus implement a shift to a broader approach to knowledge valorisation and help to connect networks and improve collaborations within and between regions.

Project results

The figure below summarises the operationalisation of the ERA Hubs as collaboration mechanism, defined in the COOPERATE project. To accommodate the implementation and deployment of this collaboration mechanism, the project has developed several tools:

- A **PLAYBOOK** containing a description of each of the seven aspects (lines of action) of a knowledge valorisation ecosystem, including the hallmarks of strength within each line of action. The PLAYBOOK also contains a roadmap guiding the ecosystem along their journey towards greater maturity.
- A **SELF-ASSESSMENT tool** to measure the maturity of regional R&I ecosystems, allowing them to benchmark themselves with other R&I ecosystems and to identify their own strengths and gaps.
- A **TOOLBOX** containing 33 actionable interventions the ecosystem can employ to move towards greater maturity and more integrated knowledge valorisation efforts, tailored to different ecosystem players and maturity levels.

- A **prototype of the PLATFORM** that could serve to connect the regional ecosystems to inspire each other on topics related to knowledge valorisation and to foster interregional collaboration.

Figure 1 Structured collaboration mechanism of the ERA Hubs. Source: COOPERATE project

Policy recommendations

The Draghi (2024) and Letta (2024) reports³ both mentioned the need to refocus the EU’s collective efforts to close the innovation gap and unlock Europe’s innovation potential, while the 2024 ERA Communication stressed the need to further strengthen and better connect the R&I ecosystems of all European countries and regions. Although there is a clear need to connect and stimulate regional R&I ecosystems, ERA action 15 “Build up regional R&I ecosystems to improve excellence and competitiveness” has not been endorsed for implementation. Different activities within the COOPERATE project have pointed at the need and the possibility to make the concept more operative and effective by further defining its scope of action, and more concretely to bring knowledge valorisation to the core of ERA Hubs concept. **We therefore recommend to connect the insights obtained from developing the concept of ERA Hubs to the ERA Action 7 “Upgrade EU guidance for a better knowledge valorisation”.**

We see universities (or university-related entities) as creators of knowledge and talent, able to fulfil the role of orchestrators of their regional R&I ecosystems. Universities contribute to this ecosystem approach as centres of knowledge production, collaboration, and coordination. Initially working within triple-helix relationships involving academia,

³ Draghi, M. (2024). The future of European competitiveness: Report by Mario Draghi. Brussels: European Commission; Letta, E. (2024). Much more than a market: Utilizing the full potential of the Single Market as a driver of Europe's competitive sustainability, digital leadership and resilience. Report prepared at the request of the President of the European Commission. European Commission, Brussels.

industry, and government, universities now often include civil society, emerging to a “fourth-generation university,” where universities function as regional innovation hubs connected with industry, government, and communities⁴. **Fourth-generation universities** contribute to the advancement of learning, training, and development opportunities by promoting the generation of globally impactful research and innovation; and by facilitating the valorisation of knowledge, talent, and best practices. They foster a structured collaboration mechanism between universities and all relevant stakeholders from the quadruple helix in their regions.

We recommend developing regional knowledge valorisation roadmaps to enhance knowledge valorisation outcomes. These roadmaps should establish the regional R&I priorities and gather the stakeholders around a structured collaboration mechanism, while also contributing to the design of tailored and actionable regional and national policy plans. By establishing better connections between the actors of the regional ecosystem around knowledge valorisation, there will be increased opportunities to match the knowledge offer with the user demand, as well as with the required expertise and infrastructure needed to develop innovative solutions and products (within the regional ecosystem or beyond).

We recommend setting up adequate governance systems to ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of a collaboration mechanism across actors that can facilitate the long-term stability of the collaboration mechanism. It should include a network of professionals and organisations with a deep connection with the regional stakeholders on matters related to knowledge valorisation. In addition, by **connecting regional R&I ecosystems** with different levels of maturity and development, the less advanced ecosystems will benefit from exposure to the tools, approaches and methodologies applied in more advanced ecosystems, hence fostering their application. This can contribute to optimising investments made through other EU policies like Cohesion policy.

⁴ Bogers, M. L., & Steinbuch, M. (2023). De vierde generatie universiteit: het nieuwe tijdperk van open innovatie en ecosysteemdenken. *Holland management review*, (208), 63-71.

List of abbreviation/Nomenclature

ACRONYM	STANDS FOR
COARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
D	Deliverable
DX.X	Deliverable Number
EC	European Commission
EHESO	European Higher Education Sector Observatory
ERA	European Research Area
ERL	Ecosystem Readiness Level
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
R&I	Research and Innovation
RIS	European Regional Innovation Scoreboard
VC	Venture Capitalist

Glossary of Key Terms

ERA Hub: An ecosystem of quadruple helix actors, led by universities, aiming at improving knowledge valorisation within their region.

Knowledge Valorisation: The process of creating social and economic value from knowledge by linking different sectors and transforming research results into sustainable products, services, solutions, and knowledge-based policies.

Quadruple Helix: A collaboration model involving four types of actors: academia, industry, government, and civil society.

Ecosystem Readiness Level (ERL): A scale from 1-5 measuring the maturity of regional R&I ecosystems.

Maturity Levels: The stages (Emerging, Developing, Mature, Advanced) describing the progress of a regional R&I ecosystem across seven lines of action.

COOPERATE Playbook (PLAYBOOK): Strategic guidance providing hallmarks of excellence and a roadmap for ecosystem development.

COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool (SELF-ASSESSMENT): Digital tool enabling ecosystem SELF-ASSESSMENT across the seven lines of action.

COOPERATE Toolbox (TOOLBOX): Collection of 33 actionable interventions tailored to different ecosystem maturity levels.

COOPERATE Platform (PLATFORM): Digital infrastructure connecting ERA Hubs and providing access to implementation tools.

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1. Introduction

This **Whitebook** was prepared as part of the **COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inter- and intra-regional ecosystems for knowledge production (COOPERATE)** project. It aims to summarise the key outcomes of the project and to develop policy recommendations for the future of ERA Hubs and the way they could contribute to reinforce the ERA.

The COOPERATE project has been funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme with the objective to develop and pilot the European Research Area (ERA) Hub concept, hence implementing the first steps of the ERA Policy Action 15 “Building up research and innovation ecosystems to improve excellence and competitiveness”⁵. The aim of the COOPERATE project is to create a methodology to strengthen university-led regional R&I ecosystems across Europe. It **supports the creation and development of ERA Hubs** and aims to **set the basis for the creation of a pan-European network of ERA Hubs**. For this, the COOPERATE project applies **an approach relying on co-creation arenas** in which a broader community of quadruple helix actors (from various ecosystems, types of organisations and levels of governments) interact.

The project delivers the following **outcomes**:

- A clear **definition** of ERA Hubs.
- The **SELF-ASSESSMENT tool**, where ecosystems can assess their level of maturity along seven lines of actions that are key for regional R&I ecosystems: talent, research, collaboration, governance, funding, innovation, and knowledge transfer.
- A **PLAYBOOK and TOOLBOX** with concrete and hands-on guidance to foster the maturity of ecosystems across various lines of action. According to the results of the SELF-ASSESSMENT tool, specific tools from the TOOLBOX are suggested to each ecosystem, facilitating the implementation of changes and the readability of the tools.
- The **PLATFORM**, including the compliance criteria to develop the ERA Hubs network to foster interregional collaboration.
- **Policy recommendations** for future investments to develop ERA Hubs.

The **Whitebook** summarises the outcomes of the project with regard to the conceptualisation of the ERA Hubs, the value proposition of the concept, its operationalisation and next steps to support the ERA Hubs. Finally, it presents the overall conclusions and main policy recommendations for future rollout of the concept.

⁵ <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/policy-agenda-2022-2024/amplifying-access-research-and-innovation-excellence-across-union>

2. Conceptualisation: What is an ERA Hub?

The definition and piloting of ERA Hubs, as performed in the COOPERATE project, are directly embedded in the ERA policy context. They are considered the main outcome of **Action 15 in the ERA Policy Agenda** - which focuses on "building up R&I ecosystems to improve regional/national excellence and competitiveness". In this context, the **ERA Hubs are intended to foster the emergence and development of competitive R&I ecosystems across the EU and to ensure the flow of talent and investments across territories**. However, for this concept to become operative and effective, there is a need to further define its scope of action. In this sense, based on the outcomes of the co-creation sessions, interviews, workshops, and piloting activities organised within the COOPERATE project, involving various types of stakeholders across a variety of settings, **knowledge valorisation is proposed to lie at the core of ERA Hubs⁶**.

Knowledge valorisation is understood as the process of creating social and economic value from knowledge by linking different areas, and sectors, and transforming data, know-how, and research results into sustainable products, services, solutions, and knowledge-based policies that benefit society. The focus on knowledge valorisation not only allows to work complementary to regional innovation or smart specialisation initiatives, but also to **include non-technological domains and societal and policy-oriented valorisation**.

Accordingly, **an ERA Hub is defined as:**

An ecosystem of quadruple helix actors, led by universities, aiming at improving knowledge valorisation within their region. The ERA Hubs operate within their broader R&I regional ecosystems, which constitute the background conditions for knowledge valorisation.

This definition captures the essence of what ERA Hubs represent: a **structured collaboration mechanism** to foster knowledge valorisation within regional R&I ecosystems (rather than physical centres or one-directional flows). The collaboration mechanism is seen as a flexible and light collaboration mechanism, adaptable to diverse types of ecosystems while avoiding the creation of new entities or organisations (cf. section 4).

Regions are at the centre of the ERA Hub concept, thus addressing ERA policy through systemic change at regional level and allowing to tailor the ERA Hub to the unique feature of each region. The definition of the ERA Hub assumes a **high degree of freedom for regions to decide on the focus** of the ERA Hubs (e.g. topic-specific or not), depending on their priorities and needs. This focus **can evolve over time**, as also priorities and needs change.

The action would be **led by universities (or university-related entities)**, as these organisations are well-rooted in their territories and are key actors in the creation of knowledge and talent. The university's role within the ERA Hubs is to lead the organisation

⁶ By taking a regional ecosystem lens, this approach to ERA Hubs complements the recent actions developed at EU level in the field of knowledge valorisation (e.g. ERA Action 7, the EC Knowledge Valorisation Platform, the Guiding Principles, the Codes of Practice, the Mutual Learning Exercise, etc.).

of these meetings, but **participants from the quadruple helix would take the leadership on areas that are closer to their core activities.**

3. Value proposition: Which needs are addressed through ERA Hubs?

3.1 Four critical needs for European competitiveness addressed by ERA Hubs

The need for action is contextualised by the **ongoing competitiveness challenges of the EU**, reflected in an innovation gap relative to the United States and China. While Europe produces quality research and possesses considerable scientific capabilities, translating these strengths into commercial success varies across regions (Draghi, 2024). This, and other insights from recent high-level policy documents - including the Draghi (2024) and Letta (2024) reports, the ERA Policy Agenda (2025-2027), and the Final Report of the Mutual Learning Exercise on Knowledge Valorisation (European Commission, 2022) – lead to the identification of **four critical needs that ERA Hubs should address: 1)** to foster knowledge valorisation, **2)** to strengthen the regions, **3)** to incorporate an ecosystem approach, and **4)** to strengthen universities and their role of contributing with knowledge to solve societal and business needs.

1. **The need to foster knowledge valorisation:** Knowledge valorisation has evolved from a specific action item (ERA Action 7) in the 2022-2024 ERA Policy Agenda (European Commission, 2022) to a recognised **structural policy** in the 2025-2027 ERA Policy Agenda (European Commission, 2025). This elevation signifies its importance as a long-term, foundational element embedded in national and European policy frameworks.

The Draghi (2024) report highlights this challenge noting that while “Europe has a strong position in fundamental research and patenting, unfortunately “much of the knowledge generated by European researchers **remains commercially unexploited.**” According to the European Patent Office, only about one-third of patented inventions registered by European universities or research institutions reach the commercial application stage.

The Final Report of the Mutual Learning Exercise on Knowledge Valorisation (European Commission, 2022) identified several **critical paradigm shifts** underway including the “shift from knowledge transfer to knowledge valorisation” and from “intellectual property to intellectual assets”. Knowledge valorisation represents **a more comprehensive approach** than traditional knowledge transfer, encompassing the creation of social and economic value by connecting different sectors and transforming research results into products, services, solutions, and knowledge-based policies.

Letta's report (2024) frames this need in terms of a “**fifth freedom**” for the Single Market -encompassing “research, innovation, data, competences, knowledge and education.” This fifth freedom would create “an ecosystem where knowledge diffusion propels both

economic vitality, societal advancement and cultural enlightenment,” complementing the traditional four freedoms of goods, services, capital, and people.

By putting knowledge valorisation at the core of the ERA Hubs, they focus specifically on addressing this need to develop and strengthen a comprehensive approach to knowledge valorisation.

2. **The need to strengthen the regions: Innovation capacity varies dramatically** across the European landscape, with some regions possessing advanced innovation ecosystems while others struggle with fragmented, disconnected structures. The Letta report (2024) quantifies this challenge starkly: “Collectively, about 135 million people, nearly one third of the EU population, live in places which, in the last two decades, have slowly fallen behind.”

The Draghi report (2024) warns that **future growth patterns may intensify these disparities**: “Much of the future growth in intra-EU trade will be in services, which tend to cluster in large and rich cities. Innovation and its benefits also tend to agglomerate in a few metropolitan areas.” Without intervention, Europe risks following the American pattern where “a small set of superstar cities has been thriving in recent years and pulling away from the rest of the country.”

To counter this trend, Draghi emphasises that “the EU must ensure that **more cities and regions can participate** in the sectors that will drive future growth.” Similarly, Letta argues for balancing the “freedom to move” with a “freedom to stay,” ensuring the Single Market **empowers citizens** rather than compelling relocation for economic opportunity.

The ERA Hubs provide relevant support to all regional ecosystems in the EU – whether they are more or less advanced – thus encouraging a broader participation of diverse regions in innovation-driven growth. The creation of a European-wide PLATFORM and network facilitates mutual learning and aims to reduce variety in knowledge valorisation capacity across Europe.

3. **The need to incorporate an ecosystem approach**: Traditional vertical interventions targeting specific entities have proven insufficient to address the complex challenges of modern innovation systems. The Final Report of the Mutual Learning Exercise on Knowledge Valorisation (European Commission, 2022) explicitly identified a “shift from stand-alone valorisation activities to **multi-stakeholder co-creation processes and ecosystems**” and a “shift from vertical thematic interventions to **systemic changes**.”

This ecosystem approach recognises that innovation emerges from complex interactions between diverse actors rather than from isolated organisations. The Draghi report notes that **researchers in Europe are “less well integrated into innovation 'clusters' - networks of universities, start-ups, large companies and venture capitalists (VCs) - which account for a large share of successful commercialisations in high-tech sectors.”**

Letta's report emphasises that supporting regional development requires not just financial investments but also “substantial technical assistance” that **fosters “local capacities and leveraging the unique assets of each region.”** This echoes the ERA Policy Agenda's focus on connected ecosystems and knowledge valorisation, and leads [the ERA Hubs to be defined as ecosystems of quadruple helix actors, operating within their broader R&I regional ecosystems.](#)

- 4. The need to strengthen universities in their role of contributing with knowledge to solve societal and business needs:** Universities contribute to this ecosystem approach as **centres of knowledge production, collaboration, and coordination.** Initially working within triple-helix relationships involving academia, industry, and government, universities now often include civil society in these networks, using a quadruple helix model to connect innovation with societal needs (Klofsten et al., 2019; Cobben et al., 2022).

This approach relates to emerging innovation models in higher education, such as the “**fourth-generation university,**” where universities function as **regional innovation hubs** connected with industry, government, and communities (Bogers & Steinbuch, 2023). [ERA Hubs apply this concept at a policy level, with universities and knowledge institutes serving as bases for regional R&I ecosystems and connecting those regional R&I ecosystems across Europe.](#)

Despite progress, understanding of how regional R&I ecosystems manage knowledge flows remains incomplete, contributing to varied outcomes from regional innovation policies (Klein Woolthuis et al., 2005; Stam, 2015). Addressing this issue involves supporting universities as coordinators that can **connect fragmented networks,** improving collaboration within and between regions. By recognising that universities' roles change over time - from knowledge producers toward innovation coordinators - Europe may better use regional differences to support inclusive innovation-driven growth (Guerrero et al., 2024; Belitski & Sikorski, 2024).

Finally, by strengthening the role of university as orchestrators of the regional R&I ecosystems, other needs would be addressed at the same time:

- **Establishing the conditions for talent ecosystems to emerge, hence fostering cross-sectoral mobility of R&I personnel** (including researchers and research support staff). By connecting universities with the other actors of the quadruple helix, all actors will learn to see the value of R&I profiles for the ecosystem and for their specific organisation. In addition, the need for R&I profiles is expected to increase and therefore the opportunities to enhance this type of mobility.
- **Contributing to the integration in university practices of the principles defended by COARA** (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) **on the need to recognise**

diverse contributions to research and diverse careers in research, particularly with attention to societal impact. By stimulating the development of the regional R&I ecosystems and knowledge valorisation flows, it will be easier for researchers to fulfil this type of work and universities will be more legitimised and incentivised to introduce changes in research assessment processes.

- **Implementing a broader approach to knowledge valorisation**, going beyond technology transfer and encompassing knowledge valorisation across fields, with a view on the societal and economic impact of the knowledge generated in Europe.

3.2 Value proposition of the ERA Hubs

Within their focus to help address the critical needs, ERA Hubs offer an integrated approach to strengthening Europe's innovation capacity through **regionally anchored but pan-European connected ecosystems**. Based on this conceptualisation, their **value proposition** consists of five main elements, each rooted in existing policy and research findings:

1) **connecting knowledge creators with users**⁷

2) **legitimising valorisation role**⁸

3) **cross-domain learning**⁹

4) **paradigm shift facilitation**¹⁰

5) **pan-European networking**¹¹

An important added value of the pan-European approach to ERA Hubs, lies in the structured coordination to encourage **broad participation of regions in innovation-driven growth**, and in the opportunity to facilitate **mutual learning** and **reducing the variety in knowledge valorisation capacity** across Europe. This is expected to eventually **drive economic growth**

⁷ The European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda has identified persistent barriers in knowledge transfer between academia and industry/society. The 2020 ERA Communication highlighted “fragmented national innovation ecosystems” as a key challenge for European competitiveness. Bogers et al. (2017) identified significant “valley of death” issues in Europe where academic knowledge fails to reach practical application. The 2023 European Innovation Scoreboard reports that despite high research output, Europe lags global competitors in translating knowledge into marketable innovations.

⁸ The European Commission's “Renewed ERA for Research and Innovation” acknowledges insufficient recognition and career incentives for researchers engaged in knowledge transfer activities compared to traditional academic metrics. Perkmann et al. (2021) found that academic engagement with industry remains undervalued in promotion criteria across European universities. Etzkowitz's (2019) research on the “entrepreneurial university” shows European institutions lag behind their US counterparts in embedding valorisation into academic identity.

⁹ Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3) evaluations have revealed limited cross-sectoral fertilisation, with the 2022 S3 review noting “siloe innovation approaches” as a persistent weakness. Cooke's (2005) work on regional innovation systems shows that cross-domain pollination significantly increases innovation potential but remains underdeveloped in European regions. Foray (2021) found that knowledge spillovers between sectors remain below optimal levels in most European innovation ecosystems.

¹⁰ The European Commission's “Open Innovation, Open Science, Open to the World” initiative identified the need to shift from linear innovation models to co-creation ecosystems, but implementation has been uneven across regions. Carayannis and Campbell's (2021) research on quadruple helix models demonstrates that multistakeholder approaches yield substantially better innovation outcomes. Mazzucato's (2018) work on mission-oriented innovation highlights the gap between Europe's potential and actual implementation of collaborative innovation models.

¹¹ The “Widening Participation” agenda recognises significant disparities in innovation capacity between EU regions, with fragmentation limiting knowledge circulation. Veugelers' (2017) analysis shows European innovation suffers from “subscale” challenges compared to US and Asian counterparts due to fragmented regional approaches. The 2023 Joint Research Centre report notes that duplication of efforts across regions costs Europe an estimated €10 billion annually in innovation investment inefficiencies. ERA Hubs thus represent a structured response to these well-documented gaps, offering an integrated approach to strengthening Europe's innovation capacity through regionally anchored but pan-European connected ecosystems.

and societal impact by accelerating knowledge uptake by industry as well as by policy makers and society at large.

Confirming this approach, the **piloting a** The ERA Hub ecosystem of actors comes together through a **structured collaboration mechanism**, whereby a group of individuals representing quadruple helix actors have **regular meetings centred on knowledge valorisation**. Activities in the COOPERATE project learned that there is a **need for support in both more and less advanced systems**. The less advanced AI ecosystem in Prague, Czechia, for instance, faces challenges of fragmented collaboration between quadruple helix actors, limited commercialisation of research outputs, funding difficulties and skills shortages. Also in the second phase of piloting, the analysis of the two ecosystems selected through the Call for Champions (Łódzkie in Poland and Centre-Val de Loire in France), highlight some weaknesses typical of less advanced ecosystems: the need for effective governance mechanisms to foster collaboration, clearer policy direction and strategic stability, improved access to innovation support and funding, stronger engagement with civil society, and the removal of public procurement barriers. At the same time, the more advanced ecosystems of Brainport (the Netherlands), and Lyngby (Denmark), face other challenges more related to coordination within the ecosystem, transitioning from knowledge sharing to deeper collaboration, attracting top international talent, and securing specific types of funding for scaling innovation. The approach for implementing and supporting ERA Hubs for regional R&I ecosystems of different levels of advancement, is further explained and illustrated in the following section.

4. Operationalisation: How to implement and support the deployment of the ERA Hubs?

4.1 The ERA Hub operationalisation

The figure below summarises the **operational mechanism** of the ERA Hubs, developed in the COOPERATE project. The objective of these meetings is to discuss, align and decide on the ecosystem's needs and priorities, activities and action plans, inter-hub exchanges and fostering cocreation on knowledge valorisation topics. Such a flexible and light collaboration mechanism is **adaptable to diverse types of ecosystems** while avoiding the creation of new entities or organisations.

As indicated above (cf. section 2), the action would be **led by universities** (or university-related entities), as these organisations are well-rooted in their regions and are key actors in the creation of knowledge and talent. The university's role within the ERA Hubs is to lead the organisation of these meetings, but **participants from the quadruple helix will take the leadership on areas that are closer to their core activities**.

Such a collaboration mechanism is **expected to enhance knowledge valorisation in its multiple facets** (industry-academia collaboration, start-up development, citizen engagement, policy uptake, etc.) depending on the priorities and the topics decided by the regional stakeholders through a bottom-up approach.

Figure 2: Structured collaboration mechanism of the ERA Hubs. Source: COOPERATE project

4.2 The ERA Hubs support system

To accommodate the implementation and deployment of this collaboration mechanism, the project has developed several tools:

- A **PLAYBOOK** containing a description of each of the seven aspects (lines of action¹²) of a knowledge valorisation ecosystem, including the hallmarks of strength within each line of action. The PLAYBOOK also contains a roadmap guiding the ecosystem along their journey towards greater maturity¹³.
- A **SELF-ASSESSMENT tool**: an online resource designed to help regional R&I ecosystems assess their current level of maturity along 7 ‘lines of action’, allowing them to benchmark themselves with other R&I ecosystems and to identify their own strengths and gaps, thus laying the foundation for development into an ERA Hub.
- A **TOOLBOX** containing 33 actionable interventions the ecosystem can employ to move towards greater maturity and more integrated knowledge valorisation efforts, tailored to different ecosystem players and maturity levels.
- A **prototype of the PLATFORM** that could serve to connect the regional ecosystems to inspire each other on topics related to knowledge valorisation and to foster interregional collaboration.

While the PLAYBOOK is intended to serve as a guide to inform strategy and decision-making, the accompanying TOOLBOX contains more specific tools, described in operational detail, that can help elevate an ecosystem within each of the seven crucial lines of action. In addition, the PLAYBOOK and TOOLBOX will be connected to the PLATFORM and the SELF-ASSESSMENT tool available on the project’s website. Hence, the PLATFORM not only connects regional R&I ecosystems into an interactive pan-European network, but also serves as the operational backbone of the ERA Hubs network by hosting all implementation tools. The idea behind the SELF-ASSESSMENT is to accelerate the absorption of the ERA Hub model, starting from the SELF-ASSESSMENT. The latter evaluates the Ecosystem Maturity Level (ERL) on a 1-5 scale, while suggesting valuable tools (available in the “TOOLBOX”) and guidance (as per the “PLAYBOOK”) in order to improve the ERL. Thus, the tools provided will be based accordingly to the ERL reached through the SELF-ASSESSMENT exercise.

¹² The Tool is built around the seven lines of action that are essential for a thriving and future-proof ecosystem:

1. Research: Promoting excellence in knowledge creation and alignment of research efforts with regional needs
2. Talent: Developing, attracting, retaining and skilled individuals
3. Knowledge Transfer: Effectively exchanging knowledge among ecosystem actors
4. Funding: Mobilising and aligning sufficient financial resources for R&I
5. Collaboration: Building partnerships and developing a collaborative culture
6. Governance: Deploying an effective strategic management and coordination of ecosystem activities and responsibilities
7. Innovation: Enhancing the development and uptake of new solutions and services, developing the right conditions for it.

¹³ Four maturity levels have been identified, each characterised by increasing levels of integration and collaborative intensity and with a corresponding Ecosystem Readiness Level (ERL) score:

- Emerging: Initial development stages (ERL 1-2)
- Developing: Growing coordination capacity (ERL 2-3)
- Mature: Advanced coordination capabilities (ERL 3-4)
- Advanced: Highly integrated ecosystem functioning (ERL 5)

Below, further details are provided on the implementation of the SELF-ASSESSMENT process and the PLATFORM.

4.2.1 SELF-ASSESSMENT process

The SELF-ASSESSMENT tool collects the main indicators for measuring maturity at ERA Hub level, and for monitoring its evolution over time. The SELF-ASSESSMENT questionnaire goes beyond facts or indicators available in public repositories. It aims to collect more in-depth information that often requires a qualitative assessment. For this reason, **the SELF-ASSESSMENT process is designed as an interactive, co-creative process**, based on discussion between different actors in the ecosystem. By discussing the questions and trying to get to a consensual answer for each of them, the actors will be able to provide a more **balanced answer** to the question on the situation as is but also come to a **profound joint understanding** of the strengths of the ecosystem and its gaps. The SELF-ASSESSMENT tool will thus provide a **realistic view on the current maturity level** of the ecosystem and will help to create a better understanding of the **needs and possible actions** to further strengthen it.

The advantage of this approach is that **implicit knowledge about the ecosystem** is taken into account, including the existing or missing mechanisms of collaboration that cannot be captured in numbers alone. This is key to capture qualitative and subtle differences and to accurately assess the ecosystem's maturity level. For instance, when considering only European Regional Innovation Scoreboard data, the Prague ecosystem is assessed as 'advanced'. However, the qualitative assessment during the piloting interviews showed that there are still considerable gaps and a lack of coordination between actors. The ecosystem was thus assessed to be 'emerging' rather than 'advanced'. To be able to capture this type of insights in the assessment, a qualitative cocreation approach is thus more adequate.

In addition, **the process in itself is valuable** for ecosystem building, with key stakeholders in the ecosystem meeting and discussing strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and needs for further development of the region as ERA Hub.

4.2.2 The PLATFORM & network

The PLATFORM is an interactive online tool, presenting ERA Hubs across Europe. It aims to **connect the regional ecosystems to inspire** each other on topics related to knowledge valorisation and to foster interregional **collaboration**.

The webpage shows an interactive map, through which one receives a geographical overview of the hubs and can discover information about a specific hub (such as a short description, a statement on its scope, an overview of organisations active in the hub, and the overall maturity score of the hub). The figure below provides a screenshot of the **prototype** of this PLATFORM, developed in the COOPERATE project.

Figure 3: Illustration: prototype of the PLATFORM. Source: COOPERATE project

Welcome to the COOPERATE ERA Hub Platform

This platform presents a selection of Hubs from across Europe - regional innovation ecosystems where research, innovation and collaboration align with the objectives of the European Research Area (ERA).

By clicking on the points on the map which represent Hubs, you can discover more information about each Hub, such as a short description, a scope statement, an overview of organisations which are active in the Hub and the Hub's overall maturity score.

The platform is designed to inspire emerging or aspiring ERA Hubs, provide context for potential collaboration and offers ecosystems a way to compare and reflect on their ecosystem development.

Please note that this platform is currently a prototype. It will be further expanded over time to include additional Hubs.

5. Operationalisation: How to monitor progress of ERA Hubs?

5.1 Monitoring at ecosystem level

As explained, the SELF-ASSESSMENT tool is filled in through a collaborative and co-creative process by key stakeholders, that allows to capture qualitative and implicit insights of key stakeholders. This cocreation approach is not adequate to collect quantitative data on the ecosystem, as it would encounter barriers for e.g. consistent definition of indicators, consistent and coherent use of sources, accurate interpretation, etc. Nevertheless, for some elements in the SELF-ASSESSMENT tool, the piloting of the tool identified the **need to complement the stakeholder assessment with quantitative indicators**. This was for instance the case for the mapping of the ecosystem, critical mass and research output (publications, patents,...).

Although outside the scope of this project, a number of relevant data sources were already explored to address this observation. The main criteria in this screening included relevance (complementarity to the SELF-ASSESSMENT tool), availability of indicators at regional level, covering a sufficient geographical range, and timeliness of the indicators. Further detailed exploration would be needed, yet this first screening showed that **several data sources are relevant** for this purpose. Nevertheless, there is a **variety in specificity and completeness**. Some sources are relatively complete in terms of data availability; other sources are less complete but contain specifically relevant indicators (e.g. on university-business collaboration, institutional information or impacts). Interesting sources are for instance:

- European Regional innovation scoreboard (RIS)¹⁴: indicators for mapping and on investments, innovation activities, impacts, etc.
- EHESO Benchmark¹⁵: indicators for mapping and on teaching & learning, knowledge transfer, research, regional engagement, etc.
- Technology centre mapping¹⁶ and European Cluster Collaboration Platform¹⁷: indicators for mapping.

The boxes below provide three examples of quantitative indicators that can complement the SELF-ASSESSMENT tool, applied to the pilot regions of the COOPERATE project - Łódzkie (PL), Noord Brabant (NL), Copenhagen area (DK), Praha (CZ), and Centre-Val de Loire (FR).

At the same time, the SELF-ASSESSMENT tool could also be **complemented by qualitative progress monitoring**. Organisations in the ecosystem could be asked to share on a regular basis examples on knowledge sharing and collaboration. This was for instance a strategic choice in the Oslo Science City hub to avoid a narrow focus on predefined metrics and instead allow space for learning, adaptation, and broader impact (see box in section 6). Also, an

¹⁴ <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris>

¹⁵ <https://eter-project.com/data/data-for-download-and-visualisations/benchmarking/>

¹⁶ <https://monitor-industrial-ecosystems.ec.europa.eu/technology-centre/mapping>

¹⁷ <https://reporting.clustercollaboration.eu/region>

example from Science City Lyngby (SCL) illustrates the value of qualitative monitoring. An SCL conference brought together diverse local actors (government, university, industry and civil society) on the subject of 'large companies collaborating with startups'. The conference turned out to be the starting point for three large companies to keep meeting on a regular basis and share best practices regarding their collaboration with the university's startup environment.

Public-Private co-publications (European Regional Innovation Scoreboard¹⁸): This indicator can complement the SELF-ASSESSMENT tool's question on quantity and quality of peer-reviewed publications produced in the ecosystem¹⁹.

The regions of Łódzkie²⁰ and Praha²¹ show an overall upward trend, with more publications from public-private collaboration in the region over time. The figures for Noord Brabant²² and Centre-Val de Loire²³ remain within a relatively stable range, with a small decrease in 2023 compared to 2022.

Figure 4: Number of public-private co-publications over 2017-2023. Source: European Regional Innovation Scoreboard

¹⁸ <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris>

¹⁹ The indicator for Copenhagen area is not reported here, as it is constant at 295.4 publications across the years in the data tool (https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris/countries/DK?perf_indicators=3)

²⁰ https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris/countries/PL?region=PL71&perf_indicators=3

²¹ https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris/countries/CZ?perf_indicators=3®ion=CZ01

²² https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris/countries/NL?perf_indicators=3®ion=NL41

²³ https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris/countries/FR?perf_indicators=3®ion=FRB

Number of Technology Centres²⁴ and Cluster Organisations²⁵ (European Monitor of Industrial Ecosystems platform²⁶ and European Cluster Collaboration Platform²⁷): This indicator can quantify the mapping of these actors and thus complement the SELF-ASSESSMENT questions on knowledge transfer infrastructures.

Table 1: Number of active Technology Centres and Cluster Organisations in the regions. Source: European Monitor of Industrial Ecosystems Platform and European Cluster Collaboration Platform

Region	Active Technology Centres in the region (out of total in the country)	Active Cluster Organisations (of which Euroclusters)
Łódzkie (PL)	2 (13)	4 (1)
Noord Brabant (NL)	5 (12)	10 (2)
Hovedstaden (DK)	3 (6)	10 (2)
Praha (CZ)	3 (13)	3 (0)
Centre-Val de Loire (FR)	0 (61)	8 (2)

Sales of new-to-market and new-to-firm innovations (European Regional Innovation Scoreboard²⁸): This indicator can complement the SELF-ASSESSMENT question on the extent to which innovative products and services are brought to users.

The graphs show that there is quite some variation across years for this indicator. A recent increase can be identified in the Łódzkie²⁹ and Praha³⁰ regions. There was also an increase in Copenhagen area³¹ until 2021, yet in this region the figure declined in 2023. Noord Brabant³² saw a sharp rise in 2019, but a significant drop in 2021, with a slight recovery in 2023. In Centre-Val de Loire³³, a slight increase in 2023 turned a downward trend since 2017.

²⁴ A Technology Centre is a public or private organisation that conducts applied research and near-market innovation, typically at TRL 3 to 8, in areas such as digital, green, and advanced technologies. It supports SMEs in accelerating the development and commercialisation of new technology-based products by offering services like testing, demonstration, prototyping, and product validation.

²⁵ Cluster organisations are regional ecosystems of interconnected industries, firms, and institutions that benefits from geographical location, shared resources, and specialised expertise. They are formal entities that strengthen collaboration, support innovation and facilitate strategic partnerships particularly across SMEs, by offering also targeted business services.

²⁶ <https://monitor-industrial-ecosystems.ec.europa.eu/technology-centre/mapping>

²⁷ <https://reporting.clustercollaboration.eu/region>

²⁸ <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris>

²⁹ https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris/countries/PL?region=PL71&perf_indicators=4

³⁰ https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris/countries/CZ?perf_indicators=4®ion=CZ01

³¹ https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris/countries/DK?perf_indicators=4®ion=DK01

³² https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris/countries/NL?perf_indicators=4®ion=NL41

³³ https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris/countries/FR?perf_indicators=4®ion=FRB

Figure 5: Number of sales of new-to-market and new-to-firm innovations over 2017-2023. European Regional Innovation Scoreboard

5.2 Monitoring at programme level

Next to the indicators at the ecosystem level, also indicators at programme level are relevant, allowing to monitor the overall upscaling of the ERA Hubs concept. These indicators focus on how progress and success of the initiative at EU level can be measured. Possible indicators at programme level are listed in the table below.

Table 2: Possible indicators for monitoring ERA Hubs at action level. Source: COOPERATE project

Topic	Indicator
Participation	Number of ecosystems registered in the PLATFORM
Progress	Average annual increase in maturity level indicator of registered ecosystems
Networking	Number of participants in cross-ERA-Hub events organised through the PLATFORM

Impact	Average annual increase in knowledge valorisation production by type
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6. Next steps: Future actions to support ERA Hubs

To obtain the full implementation of the ERA Hub concept - transitioning from pilot initiatives to institutionalised structures with formal recognition in the ERA policy - the following actions are identified:

- **Developing a clear roadmap for scaling up:** Transitioning from pilot projects to a structured rollout involves identifying candidate regions, providing them with the refined framework, and supporting activities such as seed funding, coaching, and peer-learning. Embedding the ERA Hub model, for instance by formally recognising ERA Hubs within ERA policy or creating an official ERA Hub label, would further institutionalise the model and enhance its longevity. Considering indicators on the upscaling of the initiative, as suggested in section 5, will allow the monitoring of overall implementation and progress over time.
- **Refining governance structures and implementing motivation mechanisms:** ERA Hubs are designed as “lightweight coordination mechanisms” rather than new institutions, necessitating agile, inclusive governance anchored in the quadruple helix. Establishing flexible yet transparent decision-making bodies, such as multi-stakeholder steering committees, will help maintain strategic direction and legitimacy. Concurrently, internal incentives are important to encourage active engagement from all partners. Aligning academic career and funding incentives with knowledge transfer and multi-actor collaboration can significantly enhance commitment.
- **Interlinking ERA Hubs across Europe:** Through the PLATFORM, the professionals and organisations in the ERA Hubs that are strongly connected with regional stakeholders on matters related to knowledge valorisation, become visible within and across regional ecosystems. To connect across ERA hubs, fostering interregional learning and collaboration, the PLATFORM can be complemented by physical networking and learning processes, such as annual conferences, policy labs, and EU-facilitated workshops enhancing network cohesion. Smaller-scale exchanges, including twinning arrangements, staff exchanges, and study visits, could be considered to further accelerate knowledge-sharing and capacity-building.
- **Further finetuning and enriching of the implementation tools:**
 - **Finetuning of PLAYBOOK and TOOLBOX:** The PLAYBOOK and TOOLBOX should remain dynamic resources that are regularly updated based on new insights and user needs. Tailored instruments addressing specific regional challenges, additional case studies, and refined recommendations can continuously enrich these resources. Establishing mechanisms such as editorial boards or community feedback loops will ensure the PLAYBOOK and TOOLBOX align with best practices.

- **Finetuning of the SELF-ASSESSMENT tool in a wider set of regions and over time:** Although continuity in the SELF-ASSESSMENT tool questionnaire is important for benchmarking over time, feedback loops on the conceptualisation and implementation of the tool (e.g. on clarity, relevance, challenges in implementing the tool,...) are critical to maintain its quality and ensure its relevance and robustness. The implementation of the tool in a wider set of regions and over time, will inform this finetuning and further enriching of the tool. As pointed out in section 5, existing quantitative indicators can be further explored to complement the SELF-ASSESSMENT indicators.
- **Populating the PLATFORM with regional hubs and supporting concrete ERA Hubs to use the tools:** For the PLATFORM to achieve its objectives of facilitation, benchmarking and networking, it needs a sufficient critical mass and thus needs to focus on motivating and onboarding more regional R&I ecosystems. Encouraging user engagement through outreach and training, for instance, would support the PLATFORM to evolve towards a fully interactive digital community hub.
- **Exploring further complementarity with other EU-level initiatives:** Integrating the ERA Hub Framework Model with broader European R&I initiatives, including European Innovation Ecosystems and Regional Innovation Valleys, is crucial for maximising synergies and avoiding duplication. Connections with thematic innovation clusters and mission-oriented networks (e.g., Hydrogen Valleys) and talent mobility programs (e.g., ERA Talent Platform, MSCA programs) will further enrich the ERA Hub initiative, contributing to a cohesive European innovation landscape.

Below, we include a box on the case of **Oslo Science City in Norway**. An interview with a representative of Oslo Science City³⁴ allowed to identify a number of challenges faced, as well as the main lessons learned throughout the development of the ecosystem, which may provide **inspiration for the next steps in the development of the ERA Hubs**.

³⁴ Interview with Dr. Bente Mikkelsen (Special Advisor), May 2025.

The case of Oslo Science City: challenges and lessons learned

Oslo Science City³⁵ is a Norwegian **platform for innovative collaboration** between researchers, startups, industry, government, and the public sector. The hub now unites 40.000 students, 8.000 researchers and 300 start-up & growth enterprises within walkable distance. At its core are the two anchor institutions – Oslo University Hospital and the University of Oslo – providing the foundation for world-class research, education and innovation.

The aim of Oslo Science City is to **continue to build an internationally leading innovation district** that contributes to sustainable economic growth and job creation. Collaboration is facilitated through working groups, processes, and events, and established businesses are invited into their work through industrial partnerships. The hub is led by a **board of member representatives at CEO-level**, with a dedicated small team – including a CEO, director, and a senior advisor - responsible for the **operational management** .

Oslo Science City focuses on **four ‘gravitational fields of academic excellence’**: 1) Health & life sciences; 2) Climate, energy and the environment; 3) Digitalisation and computational science; and 4) Democracy and inclusion. The focus thus goes beyond technological innovation and transfer and –through the fourth gravitation area- explicitly includes the conditions for a viable democracy, social sustainability, fair transition in the face of technological changes, economic inequality, etc. Next to this topical focus, the hub also links to the **physical development of the area** through the establishment of structures for cooperation between various ownership interests in the area and in dialogue with the City of Oslo on frameworks and guidelines for the development of the area.

Oslo Science City is an interesting example of how a knowledge valorisation hub concept is applied in a local context. Several of its modalities (e.g. the collaboration mechanism) correspond to the key elements in the conceptualisation of ERA Hubs in the COOPERATE project. Learning more about the Oslo Science City therefore provides an excellent opportunity to **explore specific challenges that may follow from these conceptual choices, and to identify solutions and good practices**. The findings below are based on an interview with a representative of Oslo Science City³⁶.

Oslo Science City aims to enhance **alignment on strategy** to strengthen research and innovation, with a focus on **creating new business and work** as an opportunity for growth. It aims to contribute to the **branding** of the area in the rest of Norway, as well as internationally. One of its success factors is based on the **physical concentration** of the network, i.e. its unique setting with multiple stakeholders directly present in the area and the incentives to develop and utilize the space in the area.

³⁵ <https://www.oslosciencecity.no/en>

³⁶ Interview with Dr. Bente Mikkelsen (Special Advisor), May 2025.

A first challenge concerns the **alignment of key stakeholders** at regional level. As mentioned, the Oslo Science City, as the ERA Hubs, deploys a collaboration mechanism. This collaboration mechanism is directed by the board, consisting of **top executives** from the members. Including persons with decision-making power in the board is found to be a critical success factor for true alignment and impact creation. Speaking with a common voice helps to bring across a joint message to the local politicians.

Strengthening the connection to the national level offers a key opportunity to build alignment around a shared overarching strategy. Oslo Science City considers it important to focus on a **narrative that unites stakeholders**, and to create incentives for the various actors to prioritize collaboration to address the joint challenge. **Overarching national and EU strategies** on priority domains, in dialogue with regional and local strategies, would support the narrative and incentives at local level.

Another challenge for stakeholders is to **identify and meet the appropriate person** to connect with for exchange or collaboration. One of the implemented solutions is, as mentioned, to organise **working groups** on specific topics or questions. Offering these working groups **a space to come together and meet in person**, further enhances alignment and collaboration between stakeholders.

Interestingly, Oslo Science City has chosen **not to use monitor progress through traditional KPIs at this stage**. The aim is to avoid a narrow focus on predefined metrics and instead allow space for learning, adaptation, and broader impact. **Progress is tracked qualitatively** through alignment with the four strategic goals, using **showcases** and success stories to capture value that cannot easily be measured.

Moving forward, there is a significant **opportunity** to implement further strategic activities that can strengthen the ecosystem and the ambitions of the members. This will require enhanced funding – both to **build robust administrative support structures** and to **pilot innovative forms of collaboration** across institutions. Equally important are **knowledge of and access to the full value chain**, strong **competencies in business development and scaling**, and insight and capacity to formalize and succeed with **cross-sector partnerships**. Seed funding, access to risk capital, and adequate public research financing are all **key enablers** in this regard.

7. Conclusions and policy recommendations

In conclusion, the COOPERATE project envisions a **pan-European network** of regional R&I ecosystems fostering knowledge valorisation. At its core is the **ERA Hub, an ecosystem of quadruple helix actors led by universities to improve knowledge valorisation within their region**. The ERA Hubs operate within their broader R&I regional ecosystems, which constitute the background conditions for knowledge valorisation. This model enables a network of interconnected regional R&I ecosystems that exchange and collaborate across key lines of action. Each ERA hub can exist at different maturity levels, with the model providing pathways for progression.

Four elements are **central to the ERA Hub concept** developed and piloted in the COOPERATE project:

- Focus on the **regional level** and the development of **ecosystems** at this level (bringing together the quadruple helix in a **structured collaboration mechanism**, encouraging exchange and collaboration between actors and strengthening of the ecosystem).
- Focus on **knowledge valorisation** and on creating the conditions to facilitate it, while maintaining a large degree of freedom for regions to focus on their own priorities and needs.
- Focus on **empowering universities to fulfil their societal impact goals** by connecting them better with their surrounding ecosystem, and empowering **all quadruple helix actors** in the regional ecosystem to **connect and collaborate** on R&I needs and knowledge valorisation priorities.
- Focus on the deployment of an **ERA Hub support system** for implementing the model in different settings across Europe, including guidance on **measuring the maturity** of the regional R&I ecosystem and on identifying needs, priorities, areas for improvement and future action. The development of the PLATFORM is an opportunity to connect and encourage exchange across countries and regions.

The initiative is expected to produce the following **outcomes in the short term**:

- The **enhancement of knowledge valorisation outcomes** by connecting quadruple helix actors around knowledge valorisation topics and thus better mutually connecting economic/societal needs and knowledge production.
- The development of **regional knowledge valorisation roadmaps** establishing the priorities and gathering the stakeholders around a collaboration mechanism in a long lasting and stable manner. These bottom-up roadmaps can contribute to the design of tailored and actionable regional and national policy plans.
- The development of **adequate governance systems** that ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of a collaboration mechanism across actors and that can facilitate the long-term stability of the collaboration mechanism, even after the end of public support.

In addition, it is expected to produce a number of **long-term impacts**:

- **Strengthening the contacts between researchers and the users of knowledge** (from business, public sector and civil society organisations) will contribute towards an enhanced knowledge valorisation, and hence to economic growth and resilience at EU level.
- **Streamlining the innovation pipeline:** By establishing better connections between the actors of the regional ecosystem around knowledge valorisation, there will be increased opportunities to match the knowledge offer with the user demand, as well as with the required expertise and infrastructure needed to develop innovative solutions and products (within the regional ecosystem or beyond).
- **Placing universities as orchestrators of knowledge valorisation efforts** will reinforce the societal role of these institutions, increase the incentives for the institutions and the researchers to get involved in knowledge valorisation initiatives, and contribute to the efforts towards the reform of research assessment processes.
- **Learning from the best and closing the gap:** By connecting regional R&I ecosystems with different levels of maturity and development, the less advanced ecosystems will benefit from exposure to the tools, approaches and methodologies applied in more advanced ecosystems, hence fostering their application. This can contribute to optimising investments made through other EU policies like Cohesion policy.

The four focus points of the concept and its expected outcomes (as summarised above) inspire the following general **policy recommendations**:

- The Draghi (2024) and Letta (2024) reports both mentioned the need to refocus the EU's collective efforts to close the innovation gap and unlock Europe's innovation potential, while the 2024 ERA Communication stressed the need to further strengthen and better connect the R&I ecosystems of all European countries and regions. Although there is a clear need to connect and stimulate regional R&I ecosystems, ERA action 15 "Build up regional R&I ecosystems to improve excellence and competitiveness" has not been endorsed for implementation. Different activities within the COOPERATE project have pointed at the need and the possibility to make the concept more operative and effective by further defining its scope of action, and more concretely to bring knowledge valorisation to the core of ERA Hubs concept. **We therefore recommend to connect the insights obtained from developing the concept of ERA Hubs to the ERA Action 7 "Upgrade EU guidance for a better knowledge valorisation".**
- **We see universities (or university-related entities) as creators of knowledge and talent, able to fulfil the role of orchestrators of their regional R&I ecosystems.** Universities contribute to this ecosystem approach as centres of knowledge production, collaboration, and coordination. Initially working within triple-helix relationships involving academia, industry, and government, universities now often include civil society, emerging to a "fourth-generation university," where universities function as regional innovation hubs connected with industry, government, and communities (Bogers & Steinbuch, 2023).

Fourth-generation universities contribute to the advancement of learning, training, and development opportunities by promoting the generation of globally impactful research and innovation; and by facilitating the valorisation of knowledge, talent, and best practices. They foster a structured collaboration mechanism between universities and all relevant stakeholders from the quadruple helix in their regions.

- **We recommend developing regional knowledge valorisation roadmaps to enhance knowledge valorisation outcomes.** These roadmaps should establish the regional R&I priorities and gather the stakeholders around a structured collaboration mechanism, while also contributing to the design of tailored and actionable regional and national policy plans. By establishing better connections between the actors of the regional ecosystem around knowledge valorisation, there will be increased opportunities to match the knowledge offer with the user demand, as well as with the required expertise and infrastructure needed to develop innovative solutions and products (within the regional ecosystem or beyond).
- **We recommend setting up adequate governance systems to ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of a collaboration mechanism across actors** that can facilitate the long-term stability of the collaboration mechanism. It should include a network of professionals and organisations with a deep connection with the regional stakeholders on matters related to knowledge valorisation. In addition, by **connecting regional R&I ecosystems** with different levels of maturity and development, the less advanced ecosystems will benefit from exposure to the tools, approaches and methodologies applied in more advanced ecosystems, hence fostering their application. This can contribute to optimising investments made through other EU policies like Cohesion policy.

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